

CUSTOMER CENTRIC GOVERNANCE IN DELIVERING SERVICES IN THE LGU OF SANTA ROSA CITY LAGUNA

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ABSTRACT

The study investigates how customer centric approach can ultimately impact the service delivery in the LGU of Santa Rosa City Laguna, this is through analyzing how the following customer centric elements such as customer development, customer experience and customer satisfaction affects the effectiveness, efficiency, and economy of the said local government unit. In addition, although the customer centricity approach is most commonly utilized in the private sector, this is proven to be effective in the public sector if executed excellently. This research aims to gauge the level of service delivery and how it can be further improved through the customer centric framework. Furthermore, this research aims to check how relevant the service delivery of Santa Rosa City, Laguna LGU, is in the experience era wherein most of the customers are inclined to use digital and technology at its full potential for ease and convenience. Lastly, one of the main purposes of this study is to analyze and recommend a few customer centric activities and initiatives from public organizations all over the world, taking into consideration the mindset of thinking globally but acting locally. Through customer centricity, the LGU of Santa Rosa Laguna can materialize their mantra of “SERBISYONG MAKATAO, LUNGSOD NA MAKABAGO.”

Keywords: *Customer Centric approach, Customer Development, Customer Experience, Customer Satisfaction.*

INTRODUCTION

Customer centricity is a philosophy and approach that is commonly used in the business world. It is a concept wherein organizations place their respective customers at the center of all organizational strategies, decisions and activities. Furthermore, the heart of the concept revolves around understanding how an organization can better understand their customers and serve them better or solve their dilemma with the best approach whether it be via product or service, on a simpler term businesses would want to know the preferences, behaviors, needs and wants of the customers so that they can create solutions or give added value and most especially deliver nothing less than exceptional experiences. In the current digital era, customers in the private sector are increasingly expecting higher standards and nothing less than greater satisfaction from the products and services they receive or purchase. The constant and consistent availability and digital connectivity of personalized customer experiences are currently shaping the expectations of customers towards their governmental services. Currently, these are directly compared to the private sector in terms of the following: convenience, experience and personalization. Experience refers to the ease with which services can be obtained through various channels. Experience is about having smooth, uninterrupted experiences that demand minimal effort to participate. And lastly, personalization deals with the process of customizing something to suit the specific needs, preferences, or circumstances of individuals, taking into account factors such as their location, situation, or state of mind. Comprehending this is crucial for the effective implementation of the public organizations overarching goal to revolutionize the interaction between customers and the public sector, by empowering customers and being more attentive to their needs, wants and demands. Citizens' expectations of public services are aligning with consumer-grade expectations, even though there may be disparities in the nature of the connection as citizens and customers exhibit nuanced distinctions.

Literature Review

Murray J. (2018) defines customer centricity as working with the right customers for the organization's strategic benefit. This is done in the private sector to profit. With existing and future resources, the public sector aims to deliver inventive results. Working with the appropriate customers strategically gives the organization an edge. The actual understanding of customers, program priorities, and cooperatively designing innovative ways to manage the country's natural resources for present and future generations comes from our customers.

According to Payne A. (2023), The focus on customer-centricity in the public sector can significantly impact strategy, governance, and personnel. For instance, it is imperative that all services provided by the public sector are meticulously tailored to fulfill customer requirements and effectively address the entirety of the problem at hand.

As noted by Stork J. (2022), understanding citizens' needs, expectations, and perceptions and providing them with tools to assist satisfy those needs and expectations are two very different things from making sure citizens are not only using the resources

but are using them appropriately. This is not intended in a dark, Orwellian mind-controlling manner. To ensure that the investment is not wasted, it simply entails actively ensuring that citizens understand and use the technologies.

Inianam M. (2023) states that a customer-centric culture starts with understanding customers and their needs. This involves actively listening to their input, tracking their pleasure, and frequently surveying them about their experiences with your company. Executives may better understand their consumers' needs and make better decisions by collecting and analyzing this data. CRM systems are effective in collecting this data. These technologies allow government agencies to track and analyze consumer contacts, feedback, and preferences to better understand customer demands. This data can then be used to improve and tailor services to specific needs. Understanding customer needs helps government agencies improve efficiency and effectiveness, increasing public happiness.

Lastly, as mentioned by Carr P. (2022), the pandemic has accelerated the implementation of a novel governmental framework. There is a growing need for swift, vigorous, and adaptable government intervention, due to the ongoing rise and expansion of digital consumerism. This has illuminated the importance of efficient government service provision for the overall experiences and welfare of individual citizens and the broader communities they comprise.

Research Questions

The research aims to assess the customer centric governance in delivering services in the LGU of Santa Rosa City. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the demographic information of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. Name,
 - b. Age,
 - c. Address, and
 - d. Profession?
2. What is the level of effectiveness for Customer centric governance in delivering services in the LGU of Santa Rosa City Laguna in terms of:
Customer Centric Elements;
 - A. Customer Development.
 - B. Customer Experience, and
 - C. Customer Satisfaction?
3. What is the level of customer centric impact on the economy, effectiveness and efficiency based on the services that the LGU of Sta. Rosa City provides for their community?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the effectiveness of service delivery that the LGU of Santa Rosa City Laguna provides to their community and the customer centric elements?

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive research strategy was employed in this study. The research focuses on assessing the Customer Centric Governance in Delivering services in the local government unit of Santa Rosa City Laguna. The respondents are from the working class that are currently residing within the City of Santa Rosa Laguna, and are the end-users of the services that are provided by the LGU. Furthermore, the study wants to saturate the area completely, the working group of the community are divided per barangay (40-56 respondents). The data was gathered from all the barangays located at Santa Rosa City Laguna for the demographic profile of the respondents, the extent of knowledge of the communities, and the perception of residents with regards to the current policies, city ordinances and initiatives of the LGU with respect to customer centricity.

The research instrument in this study was a self-made form questionnaire. It was used for approval by the concerned respondents before the questionnaire in the form of an online checklist was used to gather information and data concerning the problem areas covered in the study. The questionnaire consists of three parts. The first part is about the profile of the respondents; the second part was the assessment of customer centric elements (customer centric development, experience and satisfaction), and the third was about the level of impact on the 3e's of public administration (economy, effectiveness and efficiency). A Five-Likert scale checklist was reflected therein with the equivalent range and verbal interpretation to avoid mental torture on behalf of the respondents in answering the questionnaire. To add, the researcher conducted Cronbach's alpha test which presents the consistency reliability statistics. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients are all above the recommended value of 0.7 showing the instrument to reach acceptable reliability. The researchers used the weighted and the standard deviation. The researchers used computed and tabular values to determine the significant value of customer centric approach and its relation to the 3E's of public administration utilizing the correlation coefficient such as Pearson r , & Spearman's Rho . Lastly, the spreadsheet application is used to compute the statistical result of the study.

RESULTS

Table 1 shows that 26% of respondents have surnames from Aballera to Cyrus and 1% from Yadao to Zinal. About 16% of respondents live in Barangay Tagapo, while 12% live in Dita and Malusak. About 24% are 25-29, 24% are 20-24, and 15% are 30-34. About 12% work in business or entrepreneurship, while approximately 7% work in education or sales/advertising and marketing. Finally, 41% of respondents are professionals outside the table's categories. Aballera to Cyrus surnames reflect a grouping of families or groups in the study area. Residents of Tagapo, Caingin, Dila, and Malusak showed exceptional cases in the research population. With a significant number of 20-29-year-old responses, the age distribution appears balanced. Together, they make up 48% of respondents. The vast range of occupations among respondents, especially the significant percentage outside the stated job categories, suggests a heterogeneous socioeconomic environment in the study population with varying occupational histories and interests.

Table 1*Profile of the Respondents*

Names	f	%
ABALLERA – CYRUS	265	26.11
BBDACILLO – FULO	128	12.61
GABA – IRODISTAN	70	6.90
JACOB – LYSAME	110	10.84
MACATANGAY – ORTUA	156	15.37
PABONA - RYLE	130	12.81
SAAD – UMANDAL	100	9.85
VALENCIA -WAYLAMI	44	4.33
YADAO-ZINAL	12	1.18
Total	1015	100

Address	f	%
TAGAPO	154	15.17
LABAS	42	4.14
BUENA ROSA	13	1.28
MACABLING	75	7.39
DITA	62	6.11
BALIBAGO	97	9.56
CAINGIN	118	11.63

KANLURAN	17	1.67
APLAYA	17	1.67
MALUSAK	118	11.63
SINALHAN	69	6.80
MARKET AREA	5	0.49
DON JOSE	23	2.27
PULONG STA. CRUZ	20	1.97
POOC	80	7.88
IBABA	6	0.59
SANTO DOMINGO	22	2.17
DILA	77	7.59
Total	1015	100
Age	f	%
15-19	23	2.27
20-24	240	23.65
25-29	246	24.24
30-34	149	14.68
35-39	109	10.74
40-44	88	8.67
45-49	90	8.87
50-54	37	3.65
55-59	19	1.87
60-64	9	0.89
65-69	3	0.30

70-74	1	0.10
Blank	1	0.10
Total	1015	100
Profession	f	%
Education	69	6.80
Business/Entrepreneurship	119	11.72
Sales/Marketing	68	6.70
Customer Service/Support	24	2.36
Technical/Engineering	56	5.52
Administration/Office	45	4.43
Healthcare	15	1.48
Service/Hospitality	70	6.90
Manufacturing/Production	44	4.33
Transportation/Logistics	23	2.27
Information Technology (IT)	41	4.04
Finance/Accounting	21	2.07
Creative/Arts	7	0.69
Miscellaneous/Others	413	40.69
Total	1015	100

Table 2 shows that customer-centric governance in Santa Rosa, Laguna, is extremely effective in fostering customer development, Composite Mean = 4.46. This effectiveness is due to the city's extensive use of social media platforms like Facebook to distribute information, including program updates. To increase the Level of Effectiveness of Customer-Centric Governance in Customer Development, the City of Sta. Rosa Laguna should employ online transactions to pay taxes and other papers. The 2020 COVID-19 pandemic accelerated digital transformation in the Philippines' Social Security System (SSS), according to ISSA (2022). Digitalization was used by the Social Security System (SSS) to expand service channels and improve efficiency (Social Security System, 2020). During the pandemic, the SSS focused on digitizing registration, contribution

payments, loan distribution, and benefit claims. Guideline 6, "implementing e-services," from the ISSA Guidelines for ICT aided digitization. A detailed Information Systems Strategic Plan guided significant IT system spending, resulting in seven new IT systems in 2020. Online transactions increased from 35% in 2019 to 75% in 2020, demonstrating service quality improvements.

Table 2

Level of Effectiveness of Customer-Centric Governance in terms of Customer Development

Statements	Weighted Mean (WM)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Interpretation
1. The City of Sta. Rosa Laguna expanded the dissemination of Information through social media for the programs, announcements and news updates. (FB, IG, etc.).	4.58	0.54	Extremely Effective
2. The City of Sta. Rosa Laguna used online transactions in terms of mode of payment for paying documents (TAX, etc.)	4.40	0.60	Extremely Effective
3. The City of Sta. Rosa Laguna used a website for online application, history and posting of projects, programs and community dashboard.	4.46	0.62	Extremely Effective
4. The City of Sta. Rosa Laguna adheres to the citizen charter timeline for hassle free transactions.	4.42	0.62	Extremely Effective
5. The City of Sta. Rosa Laguna engage on new trends for business, applications and permits through online system application	4.44	0.60	Extremely Effective
Composite Mean	4.46		Extremely Effective
<i>Note.</i> The mean is interpreted using the following: 4.21-5.00=Extremely Effective, 3.41-4.20=Very Effective, 2.61-3.40=Moderately Effective, 1.81-2.60= Slightly Effective, 1.00-1.80= Not Effective.			

Table 3 shows how customer-centric governance improves customer experience. Composite Mean = 4.41 shows customer-centric governance works well. Statements like "It is hassle-free and easy for all users and visitors to register via online application" (WM = 4.51, SD = 0.59) and "The City of Sta. Rosa Laguna leverages technology to enhance connectivity, access to information, and lifelong education, resulting in clients becoming digital-savvy" (WM = 4.42, SD = 0.60) strongly support customer-centric governance in improving customer experience. The level of effectiveness of customer-centric

governance in terms of customer experience is the focus. The City of Sta. Rosa Laguna makes it hard for fixers or fraudsters to intercept transactions, preserving consumer confidence. According to Aspicio (2023), those who can improve customer experience directly and indirectly are essential. You must prioritize and create a great employee experience to improve CX. Happy, well-treated personnel will tell customers about their experiences.

Table 3

Level of Effectiveness of Customer-Centric Governance in terms of Customer Experience

Statements	Weighted Mean (WM)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Interpretation
1. It is hassle-free and easy access for all the users and visitors to register via online application	4.51	0.59	Extremely Effective
2. The City of Sta. Rosa Laguna makes it difficult for fixers or fraudsters to intercept the transaction, this gives consumers peace of mind and protects them from fraud.	4.35	0.60	Extremely Effective
3. The City of Sta. Rosa Laguna utilizes technology to improve connectivity, access information, lifelong education and learning resulting in the client becoming a digital	4.42	0.60	Extremely Effective
4. The citizen charter makes the administration accountable and citizen friendly and also to ensure transparency which saves time for both administration and client.	4.37	0.59	Extremely Effective
5. The one stop shop for business increases competitiveness, innovativeness and resilience of industries and services.	4.40	0.60	Extremely Effective
Composite Mean	4.41		Extremely Effective

Note. The mean is interpreted using the following: 4.21-5.00=Extremely Effective, 3.41-4.20=Very Effective, 2.61-3.40=Moderately Effective, 1.81-2.60= Slightly Effective, 1.00-1.80= Not Effective.

Table 4 shows that customer-centric governance improves customer satisfaction, Composite Mean = 4.26. Santa Rosa, Laguna's customer-centric governance procedures have been successful. WM = 4.31, SD = 0.71, the LGU's proactive approach in providing many avenues for clients to voice problems or suggestions is responsible for this efficacy. Santa Rosa Laguna LGU can address client concerns/feedback. Citizen data provides constant feedback to help the organization achieve its goals using agile methods. A

developer could create an app to support public health during the pandemic, or a local council could use video conferencing and polling to gather insights from citizen assembly meetings to prioritize public realm spending for various projects Stork (2022). Staff (2019) recommends actively soliciting direct feedback, evaluating social comments, and reviewing customer reviews to track user responses to your experience design.

Table 4

Level of Effectiveness of Customer-Centric Governance in terms of Customer Satisfaction

Statements	Weighted Mean (WM)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Interpretation
1. The LGU of Sta. Rosa Laguna has multiple channels available for clients to voice their concerns or suggestions.	4.31	0.71	Extremely Effective
2. The LGU of Sta. Rosa Laguna staff members are approachable and responsive to clients' queries.	4.25	0.74	Extremely Effective
3. The LGU of Sta. Rosa Laguna is compliant to client concern/feedback.	4.21	0.73	Extremely Effective
Composite Mean	4.26		Extremely Effective

Note. The mean is interpreted using the following: 4.21-5.00=Extremely Effective, 3.41-4.20=Very Effective, 2.61-3.40=Moderately Effective, 1.81-2.60= Slightly Effective, 1.00-1.80= Not Effective.

Table 5 indicates that customer-centric governance affects the economy, Composite Mean = 4.32. This shows that customer-centric governance initiatives affect the economy. Respondents strongly believe that customer-centricity efforts in Santa Rosa, Laguna LGU improve client well-being, WM = 4.38, SD = 0.65. The LGU of Sta. Rosa Laguna prioritizes citizen needs and preferences in its decision-making processes, which has improved our locality's image and reputation and boosted economic growth. Development of services around consumer needs and behaviors helps government entities identify product or service gaps and match customer priorities with mission goals. These steps would improve risk management, resilience, delivery systems, and resource allocation for agencies. These efforts are necessary to improve government service, restore public trust, and boost economic growth (Partnership for Public Service 2021).

Table 5*Level of Impact of Customer-Centric Governance on the Economy*

Statements	Weighted Mean (WM)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Interpretation
1. I believe that customer centricity initiatives in the LGU of Sta. Rosa Laguna contributes to the well-being of the client.	4.38	0.65	Very High Impact
2. The LGU of Sta. Rosa Laguna emphasis on customer-centric policies has a direct impact on attracting investments and businesses to our locality.	4.31	0.61	Very High Impact
3. The efforts made by the LGU of Sta. Rosa Laguna prioritizes citizen needs and preferences in its decision-making processes.	4.30	0.67	Very High Impact
4. The LGU of Sta. Rosa Laguna customer-centric initiatives have enhanced the overall image and reputation of our locality, positively impacting economic growth	4.30	0.64	Very High Impact
5. The LGU of Sta. Rosa Laguna customer-centric initiatives continue to drive positive economic outcomes in the future.	4.31	0.67	Very High Impact
Composite Mean	4.32		Very High Impact

Table 6 shows how customer-centric governance affects service delivery. Service delivery effectiveness is highly affected, Composite Mean = 4.32. It significantly improves service delivery. The LGU of Santa Rosa, Laguna's customer-focused initiatives improve public service delivery, WM = 4.40, SD = 0.66. The LGU's favorable approach to citizen feedback improves community impact, WM = 4.32, SD = 0.69. The Level of Impact of Customer-Centric Governance on Effectiveness of Service Delivery suggests that the LGU of Sta. Rosa Laguna should increase openness and accountability in governance. Prioritizing client needs helps companies find and eliminate redundant services, which can reduce costs. Spotting service issues is easier when the client is at the center of everything the company does. When the company launches a new digital service, they may find that most users use mobile devices. Thus, their next upgrade can improve mobile functionality and consumer pleasure (The Mandarin 2019).

Table 6*Level of Impact of Customer-Centric Governance on Effectiveness of the Delivery of Services*

Statements	Weighted Mean (WM)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Interpretation
1. Customer-centric initiatives in the LGU of Sta. Rosa Laguna enhances the delivery of public services.	4.40	0.66	Very High Impact
2. A customer-centric approach by the LGU of Sta. Rosa Laguna improves transparency and accountability in governance.	4.28	0.65	Very High Impact
3. The LGU of Sta. Rosa Laguna actively seeks and acts upon citizen feedback, demonstrating greater effectiveness in addressing community concerns.	4.32	0.69	Very High Impact
4. The effectiveness of the LGU of Sta. Rosa Laguna in achieving its goals and objectives is positively influenced by its commitment to customer centricity	4.27	0.66	Very High Impact
Composite Mean	4.32		Very High Impact

Note. The mean is interpreted using the following: 4.21-5.00=Very High Impact, 3.41-4.20=High Impact, 2.61-3.40=Moderate Impact, 1.81-2.60= Low Impact, 1.00-1.80= No Impact.

Table 7 shows how customer-centric governance affects service delivery efficiency, Composite Mean = 4.34. Efficiency has increased due to customer-centric initiatives. Since adopting technology and digital platforms, the LGU of Santa Rosa, Laguna, has improved client service efficiency, WM = 4.42, SD = 0.61. The challenge with regards to the Level of Impact of Customer-Centric Governance on the Efficiency of the Delivery of Services is that the LGU of Sta. Rosa Laguna is better equipped to adapt to changing circumstances and deliver results more efficiently. Today, the government can create truly engaging and personalized experiences for every citizen, whether they number one or a million. To achieve digital transformation, governments must be customer-centric. This involves the government providing a good customer experience before and after a transaction to improve efficiency, loyalty, and public benefit (Andrews 2016).

Table 7*Level of Impact of Customer-Centric Governance on the Efficiency of the Delivery of Services*

Statements	Weighted Mean (WM)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Interpretation
1. The adoption of technology and digital platforms by our LGU of Sta. Rosa Laguna has improved the efficiency of services provided to clients.	4.42	0.61	Very High Impact
2. The LGU of Sta. Rosa Laguna prioritizes customer satisfaction, resulting in delivering services in a more timely manner.	4.32	0.62	Very High Impact
3. A customer-centric approach by the LGU of Sta. Rosa Laguna reduces bureaucratic red tape and improves operational efficiency.	4.32	0.64	Very High Impact
4. The LGU of Sta. Rosa Laguna are better equipped to adapt to changing circumstances and deliver results more efficiently.	4.30	0.62	Very High Impact
5. The efficiency of the LGU of Sta. Rosa Laguna in meeting the needs of clients is positively influenced by its commitment to customer centrality.	4.33	0.63	Very High Impact
Composite Mean	4.34		Very High Impact

Note. The mean is interpreted using the following: 4.21-5.00=Very High Impact, 3.41-4.20=High Impact, 2.61-3.40=Moderate Impact, 1.81-2.60= Low Impact, 1.00-1.80= No Impact.

A positive and substantial monotonic association between customer-centricity and its elements is found in the table above, with p-values <.00001. These correlations are moderate to strong, demonstrating that customer-centric components have a big impact. This suggests that customer development, experience, and contentment boost the economy, effectiveness, and efficiency. This suggests that promoting customer-centric methods improves governance and service delivery. Governments can boost economic growth, service efficacy, and operational efficiency by focusing on customer development, experience, and satisfaction. This emphasizes the relevance of customer-centric governance techniques for governance results and community well-being. Customer centrality affects service delivery in Santa Rosa City Laguna LGU. Customer-centricity and the 3es—economy, effectiveness, and efficiency—are clearly linked. Effectiveness in customer development and experience needs improving. The LGU may achieve its goal by putting customers first in their approach and model. Improving customer experiences may streamline operations and free up time. Customer experiences also

greatly affect the Government's claimed outcomes. Customer interactions that encourage active engagement with government services boost service consumption and entitlement fulfillment. When service quality meets customer needs, escalations and crises reduce, and well-being improves. Service efficacy improves as data, consumer input, and behavioral insights are used to build and improve services. Governments that prioritize customer satisfaction have more budget efficiency and productivity. They reduce non-essential spending and maximize returns by improving customer compliance, cutting escalation costs, and modifying service delivery models to provide a unified customer experience (NSW Government 2021).

Table 8

Relationship between Customer Centric Elements and Its Impact on the Economy, Effectiveness and Efficiency

Customer Centricity's Impact	Customer Centric Elements	Spearman's rho	p-value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Economy	Customer Development	0.49 Moderate	< .00001	Reject Ho	Significant
	Customer Experience	0.57 Moderate	< .00001	Reject Ho	Significant
	Customer Satisfaction	0.67 Strong	< .00001	Reject Ho	Significant
Effectiveness	Customer Development	0.46 Moderate	< .00001	Reject Ho	Significant
	Customer Experience	0.53 Moderate	< .00001	Reject Ho	Significant
	Customer Satisfaction	0.72 Strong	< .00001	Reject Ho	Significant
Efficiency	Customer Development	0.49 Moderate	< .00001	Reject Ho	Significant
	Customer Experience	0.59 Moderate	< .00001	Reject Ho	Significant
	Customer Satisfaction	0.70 Strong	< .00001	Reject Ho	Significant

Note. p – value < 0.05 is significant. The strength of *r* is interpreted as follows. [0, .2) – very weak; [0.2, 0.4) – weak; [0.4,0.6) – moderate; [0.6,0.8) – strong; [0.8,1) – very strong

Conclusions

Customer development is essential for Santa Rosa City, Laguna LGU to improve service delivery. Comprehensive insights into client behavior, preferences, and pain points help the LGU understand them. Through surveys, focus groups, and analytics tools, firms may gain a complete insight of their customers. By adopting a customer-centric strategy, the LGU can adapt to changing market dynamics and customer preferences, laying the groundwork for long-term prosperity by building public confidence and engagement, which are essential for community growth. Governance must be customer-centric to improve customer experience. Government agencies can tailor policies and programs to community requirements by prioritizing user demands, preferences, and feedback. Understanding user expectations helps governments streamline operations, increase accessibility, and encourage inclusion, making services more efficient and user-friendly. Governments can adjust their strategy to meet changing user needs by measuring and improving services. Thus, customer-centric governance improves government contacts, public confidence, and engagement in governance, benefiting individuals and communities. The Santa Rosa City Laguna Local Government Unit may profit economically from customer-centric government. By prioritizing citizen needs, local government units (LGUs) can increase public service efficiency, resource allocation, and cost savings. Technology may improve accessibility, streamline processes, and reduce regulatory hurdles, boosting efficiency and lowering costs. Outstanding customer service can also attract investments, boost economic growth, and help local businesses grow. Increased citizen satisfaction with government services will lead to increased support for local projects and economic activity, creating a cycle of prosperity for the LGU and its residents.

The Santa Rosa City Laguna LGU can enhance the efficacy and effectiveness of service delivery by adopting a customer-centered approach to governance, particularly through technological advancements and digital platforms. Better government-to-public communication, easier access, and faster workflows are all results of technology-driven solutions. There is less need for physical presence and documentation with digital platforms that allow online transactions including permit applications, bill payments, and retrieval of government data. Optimizing resource allocation, detecting service delivery difficulties, and improving service quality and speed can all be achieved through data analytics and automated processes. Customers are able to voice their opinions, leave comments, and monitor the progress of their requests through digital platforms, which improves customer satisfaction and decreases resolution time. Additionally, by leveraging technology, local governments can connect with underserved communities, close the technology gap, and promote equal access to services. Governance with an eye toward the consumer and digital platforms have made Santa Rosa Laguna's services more effective, open, and quick to respond. Therefore, there has been a dramatic improvement in public trust and satisfaction with government agencies. The Santa Rosa City Laguna Local Government Unit has to put the demands and requirements of its customers first if it wants to be efficient, effective, and economically successful. Customer development necessitates customer discovery, development to meet customer needs, and commitment to customer-centric paradigm. By establishing objectives in this manner, the

Santa Rosa City Laguna LGU will gain a greater comprehension of the needs of its residents. Policies, programs, and services will thus be customized to each region. Management of processes and fair allocation of resources are two ways in which community empowerment enhances governance and operational efficiency.

Establishing a culture of customer satisfaction is the only way to improve relations and improve customer involvement in community activities. This would result in a more encouraged local citizens who are more likely to participate in community projects, which increases public participation in the local economy and may attract investors, large organizations, and entrepreneurs to Santa Rosa Laguna. Thus, the customer-centered strategy will spread a similar model that benefits Santa Rosa Laguna and its residents. To fulfill mission goals, “The City of Santa Rosa shall be a model in local governance effectively responding to the welfare of its people through innovative policies and programs, and integrated strategy anchored on.

- Creation of a business-friendly and competitive climate.
- Support for poverty alleviation and capability building, and establishment of priority infrastructures.
- Protection of environment and promotion of a healthy lifestyle.
- Maintenance of peaceful, orderly and disaster-resilient communities.”

Recommendations

The study suggests that the LGU of Santa Rosa City Laguna improve its customer database to retain and use all consumer data in line with Republic Act No. 10173, the Data Privacy Act of 2012. This advice can be achieved through surveys, forms, questionnaires, transaction history, etc. By understanding their consumers, the LGU of Santa Rosa City Laguna can provide exceptional service. Once the LGU has an adequate customer database, they can validate it to see if their current processes are still relevant to customer preferences. This data validation will help them create a customer journey map to strategically identify customer pain points and solve them, resulting in more seamless, frictionless, and hassle-free transactions. Finally, the study suggests that Santa Rosa City Laguna LGU uses online banking and other digital payment systems to enhance their online payment options. Local Government Unit (LGU) efficiency improves with this convenience. Online payments reduce paperwork and errors and allow payments 24/7, potentially increasing revenue. Electronic data enhances transparency and accountability, while digital wallets promote financial inclusion. The modern local government entity of Santa Rosa City Laguna benefits from online payments' ability to eliminate physical contact in a time of worldwide public health awareness. Online payment methods simplify government services, improve citizen happiness, and boost local economies.

The researcher suggests that the LGU of Santa Rosa City Laguna improve customer service by empowering the frontline, automating operations, digitalizing antiquated processes, and using mystery shoppers. Starting with frontline staff training and seminars on how to deliver excellent customer service at all times, the LGU can

empower them. If LGU internal customers or employees are motivated, well-trained, equipped, and empowered, they can and will serve their customers at excellent levels. Automating repetitive, redundant, and easy tasks is process automation. This suggests that system, machine learning, or artificial intelligence-based tasks should be done so that personnel can be more creative or productive. Permit applications, tax payments, and fee processing can be automated. Implementing an automated system may seem difficult, but it would save operating costs, improve productivity and efficiency, and increase customer happiness by allowing online transactions without visiting physical stores. Government personnel should not be fired using process automation. Instead, the LGU should reallocate the workers to other duties or divisions to maximize their value and improve corporate performance and customer service. Digitalizing outdated processes can streamline them and improve customer satisfaction since manual or outdated processes are more likely to annoy customers and slow down processes. Finally, mystery shopping can boost consumer satisfaction in Santa Rosa Laguna. Mystery shoppers can assist LGUs identify client pain points and areas for improvement or opportunities they can substantially improve. This effort assesses the LGU's customer service and allows them to improve it.

To provide good service, the study suggests that the LGU of Santa Rosa City Laguna actively and strategically deploy customer-centric customer satisfaction measurements. This can be done by aggressively seeking consumer input, producing appropriate analytics, social media reviews, and customer complaints. Authentic feedback helps the LGU of Santa Rosa City Laguna assess their current service delivery to customers. By actively seeking genuine feedback, the LGU can identify areas for improvement and addition to the current process to improve customer journey and satisfaction. The LGU of Santa Rosa Laguna can improve service quality and customer happiness by generating relevant KPIs. Most customers provide reviews in the comments or via messages on social media, which are unread or unheard by the LGU. These clients can help the LGU assess service delivery and gain back their trust by addressing their complaints. Finally, the LGU can use customer complaints to improve service performance. Proper complaint management and an action plan can help the LGU increase customer experience and satisfaction.

The researcher suggests the LGU of Santa Rosa City Laguna use a holistic customer-centric approach to provide exceptional service. Making service delivery customer-centric is a paradigm change. Customers are the major stakeholders in this strategy; therefore, service customization is guided by their needs. The Santa Rosa City Laguna Local Government Unit should prioritize customer service beyond politeness and convenience. That requires aggressively gathering client feedback through surveys, focus groups, and online platforms. This data will help the Local Government Unit of Santa Rosa City Laguna identify common issues, preferred communication methods (phone, internet, and social media), and the demographics of service users. This knowledge helps the Local Government Unit of Santa Rosa City Laguna enhance operations and improve usability. Customer centricity greatly impacts service delivery. Citizens are happier with services that are easily accessible, efficient, and customized to their requirements. Citizens and the Santa Rosa City Laguna Local Government Unit will gain confidence

and cooperation. Customers become more interested and dedicated to their community when they feel heard, and their needs met. This encourages residents and the Santa Rosa City Laguna local government to work together to improve the community. Customer centricity is a strategic investment, not just a service mindset. Santa Rosa Laguna's local government unit can boost economic growth by prioritizing customer happiness.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research adheres to all ethical standards, written informed consent was obtained from all participants with respect to the guidelines and guidance of Data Privacy Act of 2012 no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely and solely for research purposes. In addition, the researcher does not endorse any brand/company and organization that was mentioned in this study.

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